

Research priorities for those who are affected by Community Acquired Pneumonia (CAP)

This is a survey for people affected by community-acquired pneumonia, their loved ones, carers, friends, and health professionals. It aims to discover the most important research questions for community-acquired pneumonia going forward. It is run by North Bristol NHS Trust in concert with the James Lind Alliance.

For more information about the JLA visit <https://www.jla.nihr.ac.uk/>

The results of this survey will feed into a number of meetings to generate a list of priorities for research into community acquired pneumonia.

What is Community-Acquired Pneumonia (CAP)?

Community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) is a lung infection. It can be caused by various germs, including bacteria, viruses, and fungi. CAP can affect people of all ages, but it's more common and can be more serious in older adults, young children, and people with weakened immune systems or other health conditions. CAP is a significant health concern and can range from mild to severe. Proper diagnosis, treatment, and management of CAP are crucial for patients and public health.

1. Who can complete this survey?

If you are UK-based, aged 16+ and:

- Have experienced community-acquired pneumonia
- Are a relative, loved one, or friend of someone who has had CAP
- Are a carer for someone who has had CAP
- Have been bereaved due to CAP
- Are a UK-based healthcare professional or a clinically-active researcher working with people affected by CAP

What is 'out of scope' of this survey?

- CAP is a huge area of research. In order to maximise the usefulness of this survey some areas are 'out of scope'. Therefore, we ask that questions related to the following areas are NOT included:
- Hospital-acquired pneumonia, this is pneumonia caught when in hospital specifically (usually after a few days in hospital).
- The diagnosis, management, or follow-up of COVID-19 infection specifically.
- The broader epidemiology of CAP (i.e. how common it is) or particular microorganisms that cause pneumonia
- CAP in children (<16 years of age).
- Vaccines and other preventative measures
- The management of CAP outside the UK,

Eligibility screening

2. Are you UK-based?

- Yes
- No

3. Do you have a connection to CAP?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

4. Which one of the following best describes you? *

- A person who has had CAP
- A carer (including professional carer) of someone who had CAP
- A loved one/friend of someone with CAP
- Someone who has been bereaved due to CAP
- A healthcare professional working with people affected by CAP

5. If you had pneumonia, where did you receive treatment? (tick all that apply)

- Where you usually live
- Hospital
- Urgent care centre
- Intensive care unit
- I have not had pneumonia

Questions you want answered by research

We want to help researchers understand what questions you most want answers to about CAP.

These could relate to any topic, such as:

- **Causes**
- **Diagnosis (how we work out who has CAP)**
- **Treatment**
- **Impacts on daily life**
- **Ongoing care and follow-up**
- **Other issues**

Please draw on your experience as someone affected by CAP or as a healthcare professional. You can ask as many or as few questions as you want.

6. What question(s) do you have about **diagnosing CAP** that you would like answered by research? (This could include questions about identifying the germ causing CAP, new ways to diagnose CAP without X-rays, or how to tell CAP apart from other chest infections.)

7. What question(s) do you have about **treating CAP** that you would like answered by research? (This could include questions about antibiotics, managing CAP at home, hospital treatment for severe cases, or additional treatments to help recovery.)

8. What question(s) do you have about the **impacts of CAP** on day-to-day living that you would like answered by research? (This could include questions about recovery time, long-term effects, or how to manage daily activities while recovering.)

9. What question(s) do you have about **follow-up care after CAP** that you would like answered by research? (This could include questions about check-ups, identifying any underlying health issues, or long-term monitoring.)

10. What other question(s) do you have about anything else to do with CAP that you would like answered by research?

Please tell us about yourself

We want to make sure that we hear from people from a wide range of backgrounds, across the UK. This information will not be used to identify you.

11. What is your age in years? (leave blank if you would prefer not to say)

12. What is your gender?

- Woman
- Man
- Prefer not to say
- Other

13. What is your post code? (This information will only be used to try to ensure that we hear from people from all four nations and across a wide range of communities, leave blank if you would prefer not to say)

14. How would you describe your ethnicity?

- Asian or Asian British
- Black, Black. British, Carribean or African
- Mixed or multiple ethnic groups
- White or White British
- Prefer not to say
- Other

15. Are you or your loved one, considered to have a learning disability?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

Get involved

If you would like to hear about the survey results and how to get involved in the next phase of this project, please provide your contact details below.

If this has raised any concerns for you, please contact your GP or healthcare professional

Your contact information will be separate from your survey responses, which will remain anonymous

For any questions please email jlapneumonia@nbt.nhs.uk

16. Name:

17. Email address:

18. Thank you for completing this survey!

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